

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FIELD OF SERVICE - EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION ESSENTIAL FACTOR OF SUPPLY

Shavkat Oltaev

PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of
Economic Analysis and Statistics of
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service.
Uzbekistan. Samarkand.

Annotation. In this article, the state of the service sector in ensuring employment of the population, the number of people employed in the service sector and issues of its further development have been researched and relevant recommendations have been made.

Keywords: population employment, service delivery, small business, household, service composition, social economic policy, family business, promising types of services.

INTRODUCTION.

Solving socio-economic problems in the context of digitization of the economy requires a fundamental change and improvement of the living standards of the population. These issues require the improvement of the employment of the able-bodied population, the mechanisms for creating new jobs, and the methods of evaluating new forms of employment of the population of the regions. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, it was noted that ensuring the employment of the population is still an urgent issue: "...During the year, the issue of creating new jobs, which is extremely important for us, was in the center of our constant attention. In 2022, more than 376 thousand new jobs were created due to the construction of new

industrial enterprises, commissioning of service facilities, development of small business and private entrepreneurship. It is self-evident that since we have made ensuring the employment of the population a priority, it is necessary to give special importance to this issue not only in terms of quantity, but also in terms of quality.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT .

The conducted research is one of the main factors in the reforms in this regard. The urgency of researching the problems of managing the employment of the population in the process of structural changes and diversification in the economy, first of all, requires the research of evolutionary views and conceptual approaches of this concept. At this point, the conceptual approaches to employment are as follows: representatives of the classical school, A. Smith, D. Ricardo, T. Malbtus, the theoretical founders of the doctrine of the labor market, representatives of the neoclassical school, A. Marshall, J. Millb, A. Pigou, labor market and price - work on the basis of equilibrium, and the price of labor is considered by the theorists of market coordination.

been conducted in this regard by local economists . In particular , the theory of labor market and employment is concreted in research tasks, according to Doctor of Economics, Professor M.Q.Pardaev in his research. This is based on the analysis of labor market and employment development laws and trends, identifying the fundamental problems of these areas and preparing scientifically based recommendations on the ways and methods of solving them, developing models that serve to increase the efficiency of the labor market, and on the basis of forecasts of labor resources, the economic development of the country and the region - it consists in preparing conclusions on the inclusion of clarifications in the future plans of social development. In addition to the above-mentioned points, it should be noted that the employment of the population, small business and private entrepreneurship, the creation of new jobs in the regions due to the rapid development of services and service industries, and the preservation of existing jobs require innovative approaches.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

Comparative and comparative analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were used in the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

As a result of the long history of the development of services, by the end of the 20th century its share in the world gross domestic product reached 68.0%. Over the past years, the service industry has changed structurally. At the beginning of the 21st century, the range of services provided was limited, and most of them were home services, as well as trade, transport, and household services. Today, there are 160 types of services, ranging from scientific research to repair services, from education to services for the elderly and disabled, and the areas that use complex mental work occupy a high place. The rapid development of the service sector in our republic, the sharp increase in its share in the gross domestic product, makes it possible to solve social and economic problems, that is, to provide employment to the population, increase their real income, and improve the well-being of all layers of the population.

Due to the fact that service is one of the most advanced and rapidly developing sectors in our country, the contribution of this sector in the economy is increasing as a result of the provision of advanced growth of the service sector in relation to GDP in recent years. As a result of the programs and measures implemented to develop the service sector, its share in GDP has increased significantly. This indicator was 37.0% in 2000, 50.0% in 2011, and today it is expected to be 64.5%. The analysis of the state of development of the service sector in the republic shows that the population will reach 36,000 thousand people in 2022, which has increased by 174.0% compared to 1991. The volume of services during the analysis period is 13769.4 billion. increased by 123% in 2022 compared to 2000. In recent years, a number of decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at its development and improvement, as well as development programs and a number of decisions have been adopted in the regions in order to create

favorable conditions for the rapid development of the service sector and to increase its share in the economy . In the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, priority directions for the development of the service sector are defined. In this case, the 34th goal was called the development of the engineering-communication and social infrastructure system of the regions, as well as the service and service industries, and the following tasks were set based on these goals:

firstly, to increase the volume of services by 3 times in the next 5 years through the development of services and service industries in the regions and to create a total of 3.5 million new jobs in this direction;

secondly, development of paid plumbing, electricity, home appliance repair, and catering services for the development of household and communal services that are highly needed by the population in the centers of cities and districts;

thirdly, to establish 130 modern markets and shopping complexes, as well as 65 large and 5000 small service facilities for the development of roadside infrastructure, through the development of trade and roadside services in the territories of the republic;

fourth, reducing the share of the hidden economy in the service sector by 3 times. In order to increase the attractiveness of the service sector, providing additional benefits to business entities in the sector, etc.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 in order to rapidly develop the service sector in rural areas, especially its modern branches, to make the sector an important factor in the social production of the development of the rural economy, providing employment to the unemployed population, increasing their income and improving their well-being Decree No. PF-60 played an important role in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. The most important goals of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan are to rapidly develop the service sector, to increase the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, and to fundamentally change the composition of services provided, first of all, at the expense of modern high-tech types. Currently, the production of services is

stratified according to the income level and tastes of consumers. Along with the growth of volumes, the compositional proportions of market services are also changing. The share of new market services in the total volume of services is increasing.

In particular, in 2016-2021, the share of transport services increased from 36.2 percent to 38.9 percent, communication and information services from 8.0 percent to 12.8 percent, the share of trade services from 25.4 percent to 30.6 percent, the share of financial services from 10.2 percent to 10.9 percent, educational services increased from 2.9 percent to 3.8 percent, accommodation and catering services increased from 1.1 percent to 4.3 percent, and real estate services increased from 3.1 percent to 4.1 percent.

There are a number of specific characteristics of labor resources in enterprises and organizations in the field of public service compared to other sectors and sectors of the economy. These characteristics are the art of dealing, high level of knowledge, professional training, culture of working with customers and others. In the process of providing services in this field, the employee comes into contact with very delicate features of concrete objects and has a direct relationship with social relations, the psyche and mind of people. Prospective trade of services in villages, medical and We believe that the types of treatment, sports rehabilitation, consulting, leasing and assessment are developing relatively slowly, so we need to implement the following additional measures for the development and improvement of this sector: further development of knowledge and skills of the population in the field of service provision, use and satisfaction, homesteading in neighborhoods, extensive development of handicrafts, bakery, confectionery, animal husbandry, poultry and other industries, based on the real demands of the labor market, with the help of the structures of employment and labor relations, the vocational training, retraining, service infrastructure of the temporarily unemployed population of working age achieving improvement of the population's well-being at the expense of development, etc.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS .

In conclusion, it should be recognized that it is important to study the dual nature of services in the country. Services, like material goods, have the characteristics of utility and value, and occupy a special place in the socio-economic development of the country.

Creation of new jobs in the service sector, improvement of investment, tax, monetary and scientific and technical policies, implementation of innovative structural changes in the network structure of market services are one of the factors of ensuring socio-economic development. The provision of these services allows to further increase the standard and quality of life of the population. In addition, the expansion of the production of services by small businesses and private enterprises ensures the rapid development of this sector. Targeted allocation of preferential loans not only in urban areas, but also in rural areas, increasing the total volume of market services production of small businesses, creating a modern infrastructure and competitive environment in the market for providing services for employment assistance, and radically increasing the efficiency of the work of labor bodies to ensure the employment of the population . is gaining practical importance. Based on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it is possible to recommend the following main directions for the creation of new jobs in order to develop private and family entrepreneurship in the service sector:

first of all, it is necessary to create a system of regulatory legal documents on the formation and development of individual business activities in the service sector;

secondly, new types of business services, real estate trading, temporary free money placement, information, marketing and advertising services, accounting balance and reporting, electronic secretary;

thirdly, the organization of child education and training services, private kindergartens and schools, family kindergartens, family libraries and other service facilities;

fourth, animal care services - feeding animals;

fifth, the establishment of service facilities such as tourist companies, information and communication technology repair centers, social psychological centers, various educational and vocational short courses, etc.

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